

Overcoming Barriers to Lower Limb Robotic Rehabilitation: Adoption Guidelines for Socially Assistive Robots in South Africa

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Abstract.

South Africa faces a noteworthy burden of lower limb disability, worsened by persistent resource limitations and professional shortages. While Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) offer a promising intervention to improve therapy engagement, their adoption is hindered by high costs, ethical concerns, and a fragmented regulatory landscape. Using the Design Science Research Methodology (DSRM), this study integrated the literature with empirical data from biokineticists and physiotherapists to develop context-aware guidelines. Key findings reveal an 80% technology unfamiliarity rate, legal friction between Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) and South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA), and a strong practitioner preference for supervised autonomy. The resulting artifact presents nine guidelines, providing a roadmap to navigating regulatory friction and safely adopt socially assistive robots to improve rehabilitation access in resource-constrained facilities.

Keywords: Socially Assistive Robots, Design Science Research, Lower Limb Rehabilitation, Healthcare Technology Integration, South African Regulatory Framework.

1 Introduction

Rehabilitation services are an essential part of the healthcare system, designed to help individuals to regain their function, reduce the impact of lower limb disabilities, and improve their overall quality of life [1, 2]. Over 15% of global population lives with a disability that requires specialized rehabilitation services [3]. Despite this high demand, the South African healthcare system is faced with numerous challenges that make it difficult for individuals to access these services [4]. These challenges often include lack of resources, unreliable infrastructure, and a shortage of qualified rehabilitation professionals such as biokineticists and physiotherapists particularly in under-resourced communities and rural areas [6]. Furthermore, the socio-economic factors including high transportation costs severely limit patient's consistent engagement with therapy sessions [1].

While these systemic challenges require long-term solutions, the advancement of technology offers an opportunity for developing countries such as South Africa to improve access to healthcare. Recent innovations in artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), and Human Robot Interactions (HRI) provide the basis for the development of Socially Assistive Robots (SARs) [7]. Unlike other healthcare robotics which focus on physical augmentation such as the exoskeleton, SARs are designed to support individuals through social interaction. They provide personalized guidance, monitor patient progress, and offer real-time motivational feedback [8]. These technological innovations combined with traditional physical therapy offers a promising pathway to improving rehabilitation outcomes in South Africa [10].

However, the successful integration of socially assistive robotic technology is hindered by a lack of contextually appropriate guidelines, which complicates the adoption of these robots within the healthcare sector [11]. Rehabilitation facilities looking to adopt socially assistive robots must navigate fragmented landscape of regulations including data protection laws, medical device standards, and general health acts [12]. Most importantly, these regulations were not designed with autonomous and data-intensive technologies in mind [13].

This study is based on South African context, focusing on the unique socio-economic and legal challenges of local rehabilitation facilities. The problem identified in this study is the lack of adoption of socially assistive robots in rehabilitation facilities due to regulatory ambiguity stemming from the friction between POPIA and SAHPRA combined with high costs and ethical concerns that pose major barriers that discourages investments in socially assistive robots [14]. To address these challenges, this study proposes a set of guidelines aimed at assisting with ethical, safe, and effective adoption of SARs in rehabilitation facilities across South Africa.

2 Background

2.1 The Role of Socially Assistive Robots in Rehabilitation facilities

Socially Assistive Robots represent a class of robots designed not only for physical tasks but to provide assistance through social interaction, emotional encouragement, and cognitive engagement [8]. These robots are equipped with artificial intelligence, cameras, and sensors that enable them to perceive and respond to human gestures and emotions, allowing them to deliver personalized tasks and motivation [15]. In the context of lower limb rehabilitation, socially assistive robots fulfill four distinct roles as described in Table 1.

Table 1. Roles of SARs in rehabilitation facilities

SAR Role	Description
Demonstrator	As a demonstrator the robot displays the exercises prescribed by the therapist to ensure that patients understand how to perform them correctly [17].

Motivator	They keep patients committed to their therapy and encourage them to stay on track [15, 18].
Companion	They provide emotional support during rehabilitation treatment to reduce feeling of isolation [15, 18].
Coach	And as a coach they, adapt the difficulty of therapy in real-time, offering tailored experience based on the individual needs and progress of the patient [16].

Existing studies, indicate that the consistency and repeatability of exercises combined with social feedback from socially assistive robots lead to higher patient adherence and morale compared to traditional therapy methods [19, 20].

2.2 The South African Regulatory Landscape

The successful adoption of socially assistive robots in South African rehabilitation facilities is hindered by a complex and fragmented regulatory landscape [12, 21]. Currently, there is no local framework that provides a comprehensive governance for autonomous healthcare robotics [4]. Therefore, compliance requires healthcare facilities to piece together obligations from different frameworks such as:

1. **ISO13482** – Is an international standard responsible for setting up safety requirements for personal care robots and emphasizing on physical safety such as mitigating collisions and falls [22]. However, this standard exclude robotic technology specifically used as medical devices which then limits its applicability for socially assistive robots actively involved in rehabilitation practices [23].
2. **The National Health Act 61 of 2003 (NHA)** – As a foundation for South African health law, the NHA primarily focuses on patient rights and clinical duties of healthcare professionals [24]. However, there is a significant disconnect that exists with regards to autonomous technology, particularly the lack of a clear framework for assigning liability if a socially assistive robot causes harm to patient [25, 26]. This results in regulatory uncertainty for rehabilitation facilities looking to adopt SARs [27].
3. **The Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013 (POPIA)** – Socially assistive robots are built with the ability and intension to gather intensive data to understand and perform well in the environment they are operating in [28]. Therefore, the POPI Act places strict restrictions conditions on processing personal identification information such as health data [29]. This demand robust security measures and complex informed consent protocols before using a socially assistive robot in a rehabilitation facility.
4. **The South African Health Products Regulatory Authority (SAHPRA)** – These are South African laws that regulates all medical devices including software and machines used to diagnose or treat patient conditions [30]. Due to the socially assistive robot’s ability to guide patients during exercises and monitoring vital signs, they fall under SAHPRA’s scope. This then requires strict compliance with medical device regulations alongside the general robotic safety standards set by the ISO 13482, creating a dual regulatory burden.

Fig. 1. The South African Regulatory Friction Matrix.

Fig. 1 illustrates the resulting regulatory friction matrix by showing how these four frameworks conflict when applied to autonomous healthcare technologies. For instance, the demand for continuous data gathering of socially assistive robot's AI clashes with POPIA strict privacy mandate, while ISO safety standards fail to accommodate SAHPRA's medical device classifications. These contradictions create a bottleneck where healthcare administrators are confused by legal uncertainty and delaying the adoption of necessary rehabilitation tools [14].

3 Research Methodology

This study employed the Design Science Research Methodology to develop and evaluate the guidelines for the adoption of socially assistive robots in rehabilitation facilities. The DSRM is well-suited for addressing practical challenges through the iterative design, development, and evaluation of practical artifact [31]. The research process was structured into five phases:

1. Problem Awareness Phase, which identified the lack of context-aware guidelines through literature and contextual reviews.
2. Suggestion Phase, involving abductive reasoning to produce the solution.
3. Development Phase, where literature findings were combined with empirical data to develop the artifact.
4. Evaluation Phase, a phase that involved rigorously testing the guidelines through formal argumentation, and
5. Conclusion Phase, where the artifact was finalized and new knowledge communicated.

Participants of this study were identified through publicly available directories of South African rehabilitation facilities and professional networks such as Physiotherapy Association of South Africa and Biokinetics Association of South Africa. The study used a non-probability, purposive strategy to target experts with specific knowledge. An official email invitation providing an overview of the study and a link to an online survey hosted on QuestionPro was sent to the participants. To ensure the data was grounded in clinical reality, the inclusion criteria restricted the sample to qualified biokineticists and physiotherapists who are actively practicing within South African rehabilitation facilities, excluding participants with no professional involvement in the field.

The survey achieved a broad geographical representation across South African provinces, with the majority of participants from the Eastern Cape (60%) and Gauteng (27%), followed by KwaZulu-Natal (6.67) and the Western Cape (6.67), other provinces were not presented in the final findings. A total of 66 responses were captured, 20 participants fully completed the questionnaire while 46 were considered dropouts due to incomplete participation. This sample size of 20 participants composed of 80% biokineticists and 20% physiotherapists was determined to be sufficient for achieving data saturation within the scope of this qualitative study.

To ensure the guidelines were theoretically robust and practically relevant, a multi-stage data analysis process was employed starting with thematic synthesis of existing literature to identify patterns in regulatory frameworks, robot requirements, and adoption challenges. Primary survey data underwent descriptive analysis, where quantitative responses to closed-ended questions were processed using descriptive statistics to identify collective professional opinions, while qualitative narrative data from open-ended questions were analyzed by grouping similar ideas into common themes. Findings from both the literature and survey were integrated through triangulation to develop the final guidelines [32]. Finally, each guideline was treated as a claim and rigorously evaluated using the Toulmin model of argumentation, where the study's findings served as the evidence (grounds) to justify the guideline's validity and utility.

4 Findings

The empirical findings strongly validate the multilayered challenges identified in the literature and revealed a complex landscape of barriers hindering the adoption of socially assistive robots in South African rehabilitation facilities. Through the data analysis process, the study identified four main themes:

4.1 Awareness and Practical Experiences

Under this theme, the data revealed that a majority (80%) of the surveyed healthcare professionals were entirely unfamiliar with the socially assistive robotic technology. The findings showed that none of the participants (0%) had direct experience using a socially assistive robot within a rehabilitation facility. This total absence of hands-on exposure represents more than a lack of foundational knowledge, it is an issue that prevents practitioners from envisioning how robots can be integrated into their daily

workflows. This aligns with existing literature suggesting that low familiarity is the primary hurdle that must be cleared before secondary issues such as cost or ethics can even be effectively addressed. Without introductory awareness and pilot programmes, the “cautious optimism” expressed by participants cannot translate into clinical readiness [33, 34].

4.2 Financial and Technical Constraints

Under this theme, participants expressed concerns with regards to the financial burden of acquiring a social assistive robot (75%) and the lack of technical support (75%). This data reflect the socio-economic reality of a resource-constrained healthcare system where budgets are often set for communicable diseases rather than advanced technology. The concern regarding technical support is particularly important because South Africa lacks expert technicians and reputable maintenance network for medical robotics, meaning a technical failure could lead to permanent loss of investment. This creates a sustainability risk where the high cost of attaining the robot and maintenance threatens to widen the gap in healthcare fairness between well-resourced private facilities and under-resourced public clinics [21, 35].

4.3 Regulatory and Ethical Concerns

The 80% concern regarding legal risks and 100% agreement on the necessity of informed consent highlight a profession that is highly sensitive to the principle of patient-centred care. The regulatory vacuum identified in this study, particularly the friction between POPIA’s data security mandates and the NHA’s human-centric liability regulation create a coherent fear among practitioners. NHA is built on the premise of human accountability, however, the lack of clear regulations for autonomous systems makes therapists hesitant to delegate tasks to a robot [25, 26]. The unanimous demand for informed consent serves as a powerful affirmation that foundational medical ethics must be strictly applied to new technologies to maintain the trust and dignity essential to the value of ubuntu in care[28].

4.4 Interaction Model and Autonomy Preference

Under this theme, the overwhelming preference for a supervised autonomy interaction model (67%) over full autonomy (0%) indicates that therapists view socially assistive robots as therapist-extenders rather than replacements. This preference is a response to the legal liability concerns, it highlights the importance of therapists maintaining control of the interaction to mitigate the risk of an autonomous decision that may lead to patient harm. This model preserves the important therapeutic relationship, allowing the robot to absorb repetitive, time-consuming tasks while the therapist focuses on high-level assessment and new patients and those that need special treatment. This collaborative relationship is important to ensure that the technology enhances, rather than diminishes the human element of rehabilitation [36].

5 The Proposed Adoption Guidelines

Based on the thematic analysis of the findings and the regulatory gaps identified in the literature, a set of nine guidelines was developed. These guidelines serve as the main artifact of this study and are designed to help with ethical, safe, and effective adoption of socially assistive robots into rehabilitation facilities to assist with the treatment of lower limb. The guidelines include:

5.1 Guideline 1: Raising Awareness and Providing Training

This guideline addresses the lack of practical experiences of therapists and encourages rehabilitation facilities to implement structured educational programmes. These programmes should focus on awareness and equipping healthcare professionals in the field with technical skills required to operate socially assistive robots to ensure the technology is viewed as an accessible tool rather than a disruptive threat [37].

5.2 Guideline 2: Addressing Financial and Technical Barriers

To address the high initial costs of acquiring a socially assistive robot, this guideline suggests that facilities should explore innovative funding mechanisms such as cost-sharing models or public-private partnerships [21]. Furthermore, selecting modular or open-source robotic architectures can reduce initial costs while simultaneously developing robust local technical support networks to mitigate infrastructural challenges [26].

5.3 Guideline 3: Contextualizing Semi-Autonomous Use of SARs

The data revealed a non-negotiable requirement for a “supervised autonomy” interaction model [36]. This guideline aims to establish an appropriate level of semi-autonomous operation for socially assistive robots to balance the robot’s abilities and the need for clinical oversight during rehabilitation treatment. Therefore, therapists must retain the authority to initiate, monitor, and modify the treatment parameters, while socially assistive robots executes the repetitive demonstration and motivational tasks within safe boundaries.

5.4 Guideline 4: Ensuring Legal and Ethical Compliance

To navigate the friction between AI data requirements and the strict Protection of Personal Information Act (POPIA) requirements, this guideline suggests a redesign in the facility’s ethical protocols [28]. The adoption of socially assistive robots requires explicit informed consent from patients regarding how their physical and visual information will be captured, processed, and stored by the robot. This also aligns with the National Health Act compliance which requires facilities to establish clear internal policies regarding liability and data governance before a SAR is deployed [24].

5.5 Guideline 5: Integrating SARs into Healthcare Systems

The data revealed that a successful integration of socially assistive robot requires a careful workflow redesign rather than forcing a new tool into a longstanding process [38]. Therefore, these robots must be seamlessly woven into the existing clinical pathways for lower limb therapy [19]. This process involves scheduling the SAR as an additional rotational station during a patient's visit to ensure that the technology complements the output of the facility without disrupting the traditional routines of the healthcare professionals.

5.6 Guideline 6: Enhancing Therapeutic Relationships

This guideline suggests that the introduction of a socially assistive robot in a rehabilitation facility must not degrade the essential human aspect. Instead, rehabilitation facilities should employ integrational strategies that prioritize the three-way relationship between the therapist, the patient, and the robot. Therefore, the robot should be intentionally programmed and used to act as a *Demonstrator*, *Motivator*, *Companion*, and *Coach* to help absorb the repetitive tasks that are time consuming [16, 19]. This frees the therapists to focus on high-level assessments and deeper emotional engagement with the patient [39].

5.7 Guideline 7: Improving Access and Scalability

This guideline addresses the geographic inequalities in South African healthcare by leveraging the adoption of socially assistive robots to scale clinical expertise [3]. By integrating the robot's sensory information with secure telehealth platforms, professionals in well-resourced facilities can remotely monitor the progress of patients interacting with socially assistive robots in under-resourced or rural areas. This extend the reach of lower limb therapy beyond centralized urban hospitals.

5.8 Guideline 8: Ensuring Safety and Risk Management

While the international standards such as ISO 13482 provide a foundation for physical safety, rehabilitation facilities must also develop rigorous risk management protocol tailored for local use of socially assistive robots. Because lower limb therapy involves patients with compromised mobility, this guideline suggests that rehabilitation facilities must implement strict environment controls such as designated, obstacle-free robotic interaction zones as well as mandatory easily accessible emergency override functions to prevent accidental collisions or falls [40].

5.9 Guideline 9: Continuous Evaluation and Adaptation

This guideline suggests that transitioning from initial adoption to integrated clinical tools requires a robust, ongoing operational support. Meaning that rehabilitation facilities must implement active monitoring mechanisms to track software reliability,

hardware durability, and routine maintenance requirements. By analyzing real-world usage data, therapist feedback, and patient recovery metrics, facilities can address technical bottlenecks and update their support protocols to ensure that the robots remain functional and effective for a long time [41].

6 Evaluation

Following the Design Science Research Methodology, the guidelines were assessed using a formal argumentation method, specifically the Toulmin model to ensure their relevance, validity, and practical feasibility within the South African healthcare context [42, 43]. This phase involved a synthesis of existing theoretical knowledge with primary empirical data to demonstrate that the artifact addresses the problem by mapping each guideline to specific practitioner challenges. For instance, the regulatory issues identified by 80% of participants are addressed in Guideline 3 and Guideline 4, which provide a framework to navigate liability under the NHA and POPIA. Furthermore, the feasibility of the artifact was evaluated against the socio-economic realities of South Africa, suggesting scalable integration and modular designs to ensure usability in resource-constrained facilities. Finally, this evaluation confirms that the guidelines are practical and provide a roadmap to the unique infrastructure and legislative landscape of South Africa.

7 Conclusion

The resource constraints and shortage of qualified therapists in South Africa significantly impact the delivery of adequate treatment of lower limb rehabilitation. While socially assistive robot present an influential technological intervention that is capable of bridging the impacts identified in this study, their adoption is currently challenged by high initial costs, robots regulatory ambiguity, and a lack of relevant operational frameworks.

This study employed the design science research methodology to develop a human-centred and context-aware artifact in a form of nine adoption guidelines tailored for the South African healthcare sector. These guidelines were evaluated through argumentation and grounded in the clinical realities of South African biokineticists and physiotherapists. They address the financial, technical, and legal challenges hindering the adoption of socially assistive robots in rehabilitation facilities. The guidelines also emphasize the supervised autonomy interaction model to ensure that the robots provide the support necessary to improve therapy rather than replacing therapists. Finally, the strategic adoption of socially assistive robots guided by a framework focusing on local context holds the potential to improve patient engagement, scale clinical expertise, and improve the quality and accessibility of lower limb rehabilitation across South Africa.

References

1. Bright, T., Wallace, S., Kuper, H.: A systematic review of access to rehabilitation for people with disabilities in low-and middle-income countries. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 15, 2165 (2018).
2. Organization, W.H.: Health equity for persons with disabilities: guide for action. World Health Organization (2024).
3. Louw, Q., Grimmer, K., Dizon, J.M., Machingaidze, S., Parker, H., Ernstzen, D.: Building capacity in primary care rehabilitation clinical practice guidelines: a South African initiative. *Health Res Policy Sys*. 16, 96 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-018-0368-z>.
4. Morris, L.D., Grimmer, K.A., Twizeyemariya, A., Coetzee, M., Leibbrandt, D.C., Louw, Q.A.: Health system challenges affecting rehabilitation services in South Africa. *Disability and Rehabilitation*. 43, 877–883 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2019.1641851>.
5. Maphumulo, W.T., Bhengu, B.R.: Challenges of quality improvement in the healthcare of South Africa post-apartheid: A critical review. *Curationis*. 42, (2019). <https://doi.org/10.4102/curationis.v42i1.1901>.
6. Balikuddembe, J.K., Reinhardt, J.D.: Can digitization of health care help low-resourced countries provide better community-based rehabilitation services? *Physical therapy*. 100, 217–224 (2020).
7. Costanzo, M., Smeriglio, R., Di Nuovo, S.: New technologies and assistive robotics for elderly: A review on psychological variables. *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics plus*. 1, 100056 (2024).
8. Robaczewski, A., Bouchard, J., Bouchard, K., Gaboury, S.: Socially assistive robots: The specific case of the NAO. *International Journal of Social Robotics*. 13, 795–831 (2021).
9. Feil-Seifer, D., Matarić, M.J.: Socially assistive robotics. *IEEE robotics & automation magazine*. 18, 24–31 (2011).
10. Melkas, H., Hennala, L., Pekkarinen, S., Kyrki, V.: Impacts of robot implementation on care personnel and clients in elderly-care institutions. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*. 134, 104041 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmedinf.2019.104041>.
11. Rehabilitation Capacity in South Africa—A Situational Analysis, <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/20/4/3579>, last accessed 2026/03/24.
12. Ørjasæter, K.B., Almvik, A.: Challenges in Adopting Recovery-oriented Practices in Specialized Mental Health Care: “How Far Should Self-Determination Go; Should One be Allowed to Perish?” *J. Psychosoc. Rehabil. Ment. Health*. 9, 395–407 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40737-022-00276-6>.
13. Mtuze, S.S.K., Morige, M.: Towards drafting artificial intelligence (AI) legislation in South Africa. *Obiter*. 45, 161–179 (2024).
14. Botes, M.: Regulatory challenges of digital health: the case of mental health applications and personal data in South Africa. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*. 16, 1498600 (2025).

15. Matarić, M.J., Eriksson, J., Feil-Seifer, D.J., Winstein, C.J.: Socially assistive robotics for post-stroke rehabilitation. *J NeuroEngineering Rehabil.* 4, 5 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1743-0003-4-5>.
16. Raigoso, D., Céspedes, N., Cifuentes, C.A., Del-Ama, A.J., Múnera, M.: A survey on socially assistive robotics: Clinicians' and patients' perception of a social robot within gait rehabilitation therapies. *Brain sciences.* 11, 738 (2021).
17. Winkle, K., Caleb-Solly, P., Turton, A., Bremner, P.: Social Robots for Engagement in Rehabilitative Therapies: Design Implications from a Study with Therapists. In: *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM/IEEE International Conference on Human-Robot Interaction.* pp. 289–297. ACM, Chicago IL USA (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3171221.3171273>.
18. Dembovski, A., Amitai, Y., Levy-Tzedek, S.: A socially assistive robot for stroke patients: acceptance, needs, and concerns of patients and informal caregivers. *Frontiers in rehabilitation sciences.* 2, 793233 (2022).
19. Johnson, M.J., Sobrepera, M.J., Kina, E., Mendonca, R.: Design of an affordable socially assistive robot for remote health and function monitoring and prognostication. *International Journal of Prognostics and Health Management.* 10, (2019).
20. Carnevale, A., Raso, A., Antonacci, C., Mancini, L., Corradini, A., Ceccaroli, A., Casciaro, C., Candela, V., de Sire, A., D'Hooghe, P.: Exploring the impact of socially assistive robots in rehabilitation scenarios. *Bioengineering.* 12, 204 (2025).
21. Louw, Q.A., Conradie, T., Xuma-Soyizwapi, N., Davis-Ferguson, M., White, J., Stols, M., Masipa, A., Mhlabane, P., Mdaka, L., Manzini, C.: Rehabilitation capacity in South Africa—a situational analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.* 20, 3579 (2023).
22. Standardization, I.O. for: *Robots and Robotic Devices: Safety Requirements for Personal Care Robots.* (2014).
23. Tucan, P., Vaida, C., Plitea, N., Pisla, A., Carbone, G., Pisla, D.: Risk-based assessment engineering of a parallel robot used in post-stroke upper limb rehabilitation. *Sustainability.* 11, 2893 (2019).
24. National Health Act 61 of 2003 | South African Government, <https://www.gov.za/documents/acts/national-health-act-61-2003-23-jul-2004>, last accessed 2026/03/25.
25. Bottomley, D., Thaldar, D.: Liability for harm caused by AI in healthcare: an overview of the core legal concepts. *Front. Pharmacol.* 14, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2023.1297353>.
26. Badr, N.G., Dankar, M.: Assistive healthcare robotics—challenges in nursing service innovation: Critical review. In: *ITM Web of Conferences.* p. 02002. EDP Sciences (2022).
27. Naidoo, S., Bottomley, D., Naidoo, M., Donnelly, D., Thaldar, D.W.: Artificial intelligence in healthcare: Proposals for policy development in South Africa. *S Afr J Bioethics Law.* 11–16 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.7196/SAJBL.2022.v15i1.797>.
28. Protection of Personal Information Act 4 of 2013 | South African Government, <https://www.gov.za/documents/protection-personal-information-act>, last accessed 2026/03/25.

29. Donnelly, D.: First do no harm: legal principles regulating the future of artificial intelligence in health care in South Africa. *Potchefstroom Electronic Law Journal (PELJ)*. 25, 1–43 (2022).
30. Guideline for Classification of Medical Devices and IVDs, <https://www.sahpra.org.za/document/guideline-for-classification-of-medical-devices-and-ivds/>, last accessed 2026/03/25.
31. Hevner, A.R., March, S.T., Park, J., Ram, S.: Design science in information systems research1. *MIS quarterly*. 28, 75–106 (2004).
32. Braun, V., Clarke, V., Boulton, E., Davey, L., McEvoy, C.: The online survey as a *qualitative* research tool. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. 24, 641–654 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2020.1805550>.
33. Thordardottir, B., Malmgren Fänge, A., Lethin, C., Rodriguez Gatta, D., Chiatti, C.: Acceptance and Use of Innovative Assistive Technologies among People with Cognitive Impairment and Their Caregivers: A Systematic Review. *BioMed Research International*. 2019, 1–18 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9196729>.
34. Fardeau, E., Senghor, A.S., Racine, E.: The Impact of Socially Assistive Robots on Human Flourishing in the Context of Dementia: A Scoping Review. *Int J of Soc Robotics*. 15, 1025–1075 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-023-00980-8>.
35. Ariani, A., Kapadia, V., Talaei-Khoei, A., Li, J., Ray, P.K.: Challenges in Seniors Adopting Assistive Robots: A Systematic Review. *ITMR*. 6, 25 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.2991/itmr.2016.6.2.1>.
36. Feil-Seifer, D., Skinner, K., Matarić, M.J.: Benchmarks for evaluating socially assistive robotics. *IS*. 8, 423–439 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1075/is.8.3.07fei>.
37. Papadopoulou, I., Lazzarino, R.: Developing, delivering, and evaluating an online course on socially assistive robots in culturally competent and compassionate healthcare: A sequential multiphase, mixed-method study. *DIGITAL HEALTH*. 10, 20552076241271792 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20552076241271792>.
38. Mwogosi, A., Kibusi, S.: Critical success factors for EHR systems implementation in developing countries: A systematic review. *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*. (2024).
39. Christoforou, E.G., Avgousti, S., Ramdani, N., Novales, C., Panayides, A.S.: The upcoming role for nursing and assistive robotics: opportunities and challenges ahead. *Frontiers in digital health*. 2, 585656 (2020).
40. Aymerich-Franch, L., Ferrer, I.: Socially Assistive Robots' Deployment in Healthcare Settings: A Global Perspective. *Int. J. Human. Robot*. 20, 2350002 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0219843623500020>.
41. Gregor, S., Hevner, A.R.: Positioning and Presenting Design Science Research for Maximum Impact. *MIS Quarterly*. 37, 337–355 (2013).
42. Toulmin, S.E.: *The uses of argument*. Cambridge university press (2003).
43. Giri, V., Paily, M.U.: Effect of Scientific Argumentation on the Development of Critical Thinking. *Sci & Educ*. 29, 673–690 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11191-020-00120-y>.